

PREPRINT: Predicting rut depth with soil moisture estimates from ERA5-Land and in-situ measurements

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Abstract

Spatiotemporal modelling is an innovative way of predicting soil moisture and has promising applications in supporting sustainable forest operations. One such application is the prediction of rutting, since rutting can cause severe damage to forest soils and ecological functions.

In this work, we used ERA5-Land soil moisture retrievals and several topographic indices to model the response variable, in-situ soil water content, by means of a random forest model. We then correlated the predicted soil moisture with rut depth from different trials.

Our spatiotemporal modelling approach successfully predicted soil moisture with a Kendall's rank correlation coefficient of 0.62 (R^2 of 64%). The final model included the topographic depth-to-water index, slope, stream power index, topographic wetness index, as well as temporal components such as numeric variables derived from date and ERA5-Land soil moisture retrievals. These retrievals showed to be the most important predictor in the model, indicating a large temporal variation. The prediction of rut depth was also successful, resulting in a Kendall's correlation coefficient of 0.63.

Our results demonstrate that by using data from several sources, including ERA5-Land retrievals, topographic indices and in-situ soil moisture measurements, we can accurately predict soil moisture and use this information to predict rut depth. This has practical applications in reducing the impact of heavy machinery on forest soils and avoiding wet areas during forest operations.

Keywords: spatiotemporal modelling, forest management, forest engineering, rutting, downscaling, reanalysis

1 Introduction

For decades, forestry research has sought solutions to accurately predict the trafficability of forest soils (Murphy et al., 2007; White et al., 2012; Mattila and Tokola, 2019). In order to further sustainable forest management, efficient protection of forest soils is mandatory (Vega-Nieva et al., 2009; Uusitalo et al., 2019; Picchio et al., 2020). Heavy harvesting and forwarding machines have been frequently associated with severe soil damage, particularly when operating on soils with low bearing capacity (Horn et al., 2007; Allman et al., 2017). Soil compaction as a consequence of harvesting operations (Eliasson, 2005;

35 Ampoorter et al., 2010; DeArmond et al., 2021) is detrimental to a number of ecological functions, including soil biota
36 (Beylich et al., 2010), hydrological patterns, and nutrient supply, with potential drawbacks on plant growth and site
37 productivity (Curzon et al., 2022). In addition to soil compaction, machine traffic can also result in deep ruts (Horn et al.,
38 2007; Poltorak et al., 2018; Ala-Ilomäki et al., 2021), which affect site hydrology and increase anaerobic conditions at the
39 rut's base, where air-filled porosity is reduced, leading to minimized soil aeration (Hansson et al., 2019). The risk of causing
40 high degrees of soil compaction and rutting is mainly attributed to soil properties such as initial soil bulk density and texture,
41 as well as the current soil water content (Cambi et al., 2015; Crawford et al., 2021). Moist soils show a higher susceptibility
42 to damage since the internal friction is decreased through water embracing soil particles (Hillel, 1998), reducing the soil
43 bearing capacity and the ability for elastic responses to machine-induced impacts (McNabb et al., 2001).

44 To support forestry management and machine operators, accurate cartographic information on soils with low bearing capacity
45 is essential (Campbell et al., 2013; Jones and Arp, 2017; Sirén et al., 2019). However, existing models that rely on detailed
46 soil maps to retrieve soil mechanical parameters (e.g. Gröll, 2011; Heubaum, 2015) require a high level of input data, and
47 high-resolution soil maps are only available for selected areas, hindering their large-scale application (Vega-Nieva et al.,
48 2009; Kristensen et al., 2019). Therefore, researchers have turned to topographic modelling as a more promising approach
49 (White et al., 2012; Lidberg et al., 2020), as it requires only digital elevation models (DEM), which are increasingly available
50 for most parts of Europe (Guo et al., 2017; Hoffmann et al., 2022). One topographic index that has been extensively studied
51 is the "depth-to-water" (DTW) concept, originally developed and tested at the University of New Brunswick by Meng,
52 Ogilvie, and Arp, as described by Murphy et al. (2007; 2009). The DTW concept calculates flow lines across areas of interest
53 by determining a flow accumulation and selecting lines that originate at a set threshold of accumulated upstream contributing
54 areas. Using a cost function that considers the cell-to-cell slopes, the vertical distances from each cell within a raster to the
55 nearest simulated flow line are ascertained. DTW is well documented (e.g. Vega-Nieva et al., 2009; Murphy et al., 2011;
56 White et al., 2012).

57 Previous research has shown that the DTW index performs relatively well in predicting wet areas in forested formerly
58 glaciated landscapes compared to other indices (Ågren et al., 2014; Larson et al., 2022). Recent studies have explored further
59 developments in moisture prediction by utilizing machine learning algorithms applied to a variety of freely available data and
60 diverse retrieved information, including different topographic indices calculated on DEMs. Ågren et al. (2021), used 28
61 topographic predictor variables in an eXtreme Gradient Boosting model (Chen et al., 2021) to predict soil moisture across the
62 entire Swedish forest landscape at high resolution (2x2 m). Although topographic modelling approaches are widely used, they
63 often fail to adjust to seasonal changes in soil water regimes. Static maps may not adequately represent temporal occurrences
64 of flow lines, wet fields, or water-saturated soils. To address this issue, the DTW concept offers a potential solution, enabling
65 the calculation of different scenarios ranging from 'very dry' or 'frozen' to 'wet' soil conditions. However, selecting the most
66 accurate DTW scenario requires high expertise, and mistakes can lead to reduced accuracy and result in potential soil damages
67 that could be avoided.

68 Therefore, we believe that the next crucial step in soil moisture modelling is to incorporate a temporal component that enables
69 the prediction of rasters for any given time and area. One approach to achieve this was designed by Schönauer et al. (2022),
70 who developed a spatiotemporal prediction model. Dynamic satellite-based retrievals of soil moisture with coarse spatial
71 resolution (Soil Moisture Active Passive Mission) were combined with high-resolution but static topographic maps. This

72 resulted in improved performance in predicting moisture values across time-series conducted on sites in Finland, Germany,
73 and Poland. The incorporation of a dynamic component into the prediction model enabled reflection of the current overall
74 moisture conditions on the study sites. This allowed to calculate daily prediction grids that could support forestry practice and
75 enable the guidance of machine operators on sites to avoid traffic on wet areas susceptible to damages. However, a validation
76 of predicting rut depth by models of this kind has not been facilitated yet.

77 The effectiveness of soil moisture modelling, whether based on static or dynamic independent variables, is ultimately
78 constrained by the quality of the dependent variable, which in this case is in-situ soil moisture. Manual measurements of soil
79 moisture have been conducted in numerous studies using different devices, such as hand-held time-domain reflectometry
80 sensors (Kemppinen et al., 2018; Uusitalo et al., 2019) or impedance measuring techniques (e.g. Schönauer et al., 2021b).
81 Despite the potential inaccuracies associated with these techniques (Walker et al., 2004; Francesca et al., 2010), they offer
82 significant advantages in terms of flexibility, scalability, low investment costs, and minimal maintenance. Another option is
83 the use of continuously measuring sensor networks (e.g. Oliveira et al., 2021), which can provide relatively reliable
84 measurements but with limited spatial coverage due to the high costs of installation and maintenance.

85 In this study, we built upon the approach developed by Schönauer et al. (2022) by incorporating additional data sources,
86 including additional topographic indices, soil maps, and soil moisture retrievals from ERA5-Land for two soil depths. The
87 study also used two types of data sources for soil moisture measurements: manual measurements using a handheld moisture
88 meter, and data from two continuously measuring sensor networks. We argue that manual measurements are simpler and can
89 be applied to larger areas, while sensor networks are more expensive and limited to chosen positions.

90 The study had two main objectives: 1) to train soil moisture models using the two individual data sets (manual measurements
91 and sensor networks) and evaluate their prediction performance, and 2) to select the best combination of predictor variables
92 using a repeated cross-validation approach and compare the best models with rut depth data obtained during four trials using
93 a forwarder.

94 2 Material and Methods

95 The data acquisition of volumetric soil water content (SWC, [%]) and the trials with a forwarder were conducted in two forest
96 stands located near the city of Arnsberg in North Rhine-Westphalia (Figure 1). The forest stands were situated at an altitude
97 of approximately 250 m on common soil types such as Cambisol and Stagnosol on Claystone and Sandstone from Devon and
98 Carbon (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of the study sites, where soil water content was captured and field trials with a forwarder were performed.

Site	Coordinates in WGS84		Dominant soil types	Humus form	Slope [%]	Canopy
	x	y				
1	8.039	51.406	Cambisol - Stagnosol	Mesomull	15-30	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> , <i>Quercus spp.</i> , <i>Pinus sylvestris</i>
2	8.024	51.473	Stagnosol	Mull	1-7	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>

99 We collected SWC data through manual measurements and a continuously measuring soil sensor network. By merging this
100 data with various topographic indices, soil maps and temporal retrievals, we created spatiotemporal models of SWC, which
101 were validated through repeated cross-validation. These models were then used to predict rut depth estimated during four
102 field trials (details in Sect. 2.2).

Figure 1: The map indicates the locations of two experimental areas on a hill-shaded digital elevation model; Site1 (A, coordinates x, y in WGS84: 8.039, 51.406) and Site2 (B, coordinates: 8.024, 51.473), which were used for collecting time-series data on soil water content (SWC). SWC was measured using a handheld soil moisture meter (impedance measuring technique, IMT) along transects (red lines), each containing 21 measuring positions. In addition, a soil sensor network (SSN) was used to continuously capture SWC at 18 positions (white rhombus). The map also indicates the locations of 40 transects (in crop-outs) used for measuring rut depth (RD) during relatively wet conditions (Trial1, blue lines) and dryer conditions (Trial2, orange lines).

103

104 2.1 Soil moisture models

105 2.1.1 Soil moisture measurements

106 Manual measurements of SWC were performed using a HH2 Moisture Meter (Delta-T Devices Ltd, England), which applies
 107 Impedance Measuring Technique (Eijkelkamp Agrisearch Equipment, 2013). These measurements were saved in the dataset
 108 ‘IMT’. In addition, data from a continuously measuring Soil Sensor Network was used, giving the dataset ‘SSN’.

109 The IMT data used for this study were previously used for the validation by Schönauer et al. (2022) and consisted of 12
 110 measuring transects. The transects were placed in various positions in broadleaved forests, known to be temporarily wet or
 111 sensitive for machine traffic, with each transect having a length of 40 m. SWC was measured with a spacing of 2 m along the
 112 transects. To measure SWC, measuring rods of 60 mm length were vertically inserted into the soil after removing the humus
 113 layer. The measurements were taken almost monthly between September 2019 and October 2020 (Figure 3B). The IMT data
 114 consisted of 2,184 observations. Overall, this dataset offers a relatively high level of spatial granularity, with 252 measuring
 115 positions. However, the temporal resolution of the data is relatively low, with only monthly measuring campaigns conducted.
 116 The SSN data was obtained from continuously measuring SMT100 sensors (TRUEBNER GmbH, Germany), placed on two
 117 sites, each having 9 positions with a spacing of 50x50 m. These sites were specifically selected because they were known to
 118 be temporarily wet or sensitive for machine traffic. At each position, two sensors were placed at a depth of 10 cm in the
 119 mineral soil, with a temporal resolution of 15 minutes. The data from these sensors were averaged for each position and each
 120 of the 1,116 days captured, resulting in a total of 16,351 observations after omitting all missing values. While this data set
 121 provides a high level of temporal granularity, it suffers from a low level of spatial granularity due to the limited number of
 122 positions sampled.

123 To enable the incorporation of seasonal effects in the modelling approaches, we transformed the date of each measurement

124 into numeric vectors, resulting in the variables Year, Month, and Season. The coding used for Season was as follows: 1 for
125 March, April, and May; 2 for June, July, and August; 3 for September, October, and November; and 4 for December, January,
126 and February.

127 To enable the creation of spatiotemporal data, the positions of all measuring locations were captured using post-processed
128 signals from a GNSS device (Trimble R2 RTK Rover, Trimble, Colorado, USA). This data was then fused with a range of
129 topographic indices. To achieve this, values of several topographic indices were extracted at each measuring position of IMT
130 and SSN and inserted into the attributes of a shapefile.

131 **2.1.2 Topographic indices**

132 For calculating topographic indices, we used a freely available digital elevation model (DEM), as provided by the
133 Bezirksregierung Köln (2020). The resolution of this model was 1x1 m, with a vertical accuracy of ± 0.2 m. Using the free
134 programming language R (version 4.0.2) and RStudio (version 2022.07.2, Posit PBC, Massachusetts, USA), along with the
135 package "rgrass" (Bivand, 2021) to utilize GRASS GIS (Awaida and Westervelt, 2020) commands in the R interface, the
136 command 'r.hydrodem' was used to 'remove all sinks' (Flags: -a) from the DEM. Thereafter, we calculated depth-to-water
137 (DTW) maps. To generate these maps, we followed the script by Schönauer and Maack (2021) and used flow initiation areas
138 (FIA) of varying sizes (0.25 ha, 1.00 ha, and 4.00 ha) to account for different soil moisture conditions. The DTW maps were
139 named DTW025, DTW1, and DTW4, corresponding to the FIA used. A smaller FIA resulted in a DTW map for wetter
140 conditions, as the network of simulated flow lines expanded, while a larger FIA represented drier conditions. For further
141 details, refer to Murphy et al. (2009; 2011).

142 The Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) represents the tendency for water to accumulate at any point in the catchment (Quinn
143 et al., 1991), while SPI represents the power of water flow at any point in the catchment and the gravitational forces that move
144 water downslope (Moore et al., 1991). To compute TWI, we used the 'r.watershed' command in GRASS GIS, as conceived
145 by Sørensen and Seibert (2007). TWI was calculated as $\ln(\alpha/\tan(\beta))$, where α is the cumulative upslope area draining through
146 a point per unit contour length, and $\tan(\beta)$ is the local slope angle. SPI (Moore et al., 1991) was calculated as $\alpha * \tan(\beta)$. Flow
147 Accumulation, representing the absolute amount of overland flow passing through each cell, and Basin, indicating the
148 watershed basin with a threshold of 0.25 ha, were also included as a variable. TWI, SPI, and Flow Accumulation were
149 calculated on an aggregated DEM with a spatial resolution of 15x15 m. This approach was selected for its ability to produce
150 more robust and accurate estimates (Ågren et al., 2014). In addition, we calculated the variable Slope [$^{\circ}$] using the R-package
151 'raster' (Hijmans, 2020).

152 **2.1.3 Soil maps**

153 Soil maps of North Rhine-Westphalia were originally generated at a scale of 1:5,000 from forest site surveys. While these
154 maps are not available across the entire region of North Rhine-Westphalia, we were able to gather them for the study sites.
155 Soil type from these soil maps was added as variable Soil05.

156 By contrast, soil maps with a scale of 1:50,000 are available for the entirety of North Rhine-Westphalia. We added the soil
157 type information derived from these maps as Soil50.

158 **2.1.4 Temporal soil water content from ERA5-Land**

159 ERA5-Land is a global reanalysis dataset providing hourly estimates of meteorological variables at a spatial resolution of 9x9
160 km, including soil moisture. ‘Volumetric soil water layer 1’ [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$], one of the available parameters, represents the water
161 content in the top soil layer (0-7 cm) retrieved by assimilating satellite and ground-based observations. Soil water content for
162 a depth of 7-28 cm is given by ‘Volumetric soil water layer 2’.

163 To gather data from ERA5-Land, we utilized the API provided by CDS (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2019) and the
164 R-package 'ecmwf' (Koen Hufkens et al., 2019) to download daily grids (at 14:00 UTC) of layer 1 and 2. The downloaded
165 data covered both the measuring positions and time span required for the analysis. After downloading the data, we stacked
166 the daily grids and extracted the corresponding values at each measuring position, giving $\text{SWC}_{\text{ERA}L1}$. $\text{SWC}_{\text{ERA}L2}$,
167 respectively.

168 All data, the topographic information, soil types, numerical values of date and the dynamic variables from ERA5-Land were
169 merged with in-situ data, either IMT or SSN.

170 **2.1.5 Modelling**

171 The modelling approach described here was applied separately for both data sets, IMT and SSN (the main outputs when both
172 datasets were combined can be seen in Appendix A).

173 Initially, we fitted a linear model with SWC as the dependent variable and $\text{SWC}_{\text{ERA}L1}$, $\text{SWC}_{\text{ERA}L2}$, Year, Month, Season,
174 DTW025, DTW1, DTW2, DTW4, Slope, TWI, SPI, Accumulation, Basin, Soil05, and Soil50 as the independent variables.
175 We then used this linear model to check the data for autocorrelations and subsequently eliminated variables with a variance
176 inflation factor > 10 through an iterative process, reducing one variable at a time. Also, the feature selection according to the
177 Boruta algorithm (package 'Boruta', Kursa and Rudnicki, 2010) was applied.

178 We then trained random forest models (Breiman, 2001), repeatedly reported as efficient in predicting complex data
179 (Kemppinen et al., 2018; Carranza et al., 2021; Cavalli et al., 2023), using the 'ranger' package (Wright and Ziegler, 2017)
180 with a 10-fold cross-validation with 5 repetitions. For each of the 50 models in the validation of a model, we noted the mean
181 R^2 (according to Kuhn (2020)) of the random forests and the representative standard deviation. In addition, the least important
182 variable according to impurity and its frequency within the 50 validation sets were traced. The variable noted most frequently
183 as least important was then removed, and a new cross-validation was performed on $\text{SWC} \sim (n-1)$ variables, with n being the
184 number of predictors in the model trained previously. This process was repeated until only one predictor variable remained.

185 To avoid temporal autocorrelations at the measuring positions, positions IDs were used to select the folds of the cross
186 validations.

187 **2.2 Rut depth data**

188 During the field trials conducted in two forest stands at two seasons, a fully loaded forwarder (John Deere 1210G, 8-Wheel
189 model) was used. The first trial was conducted on section 1 of an existing machine operating trail on 2021-03-11, and the
190 second trial was conducted on subsequent section 2 of the same trail on 2020-10-11, or in close proximity of section 1 (Figure
191 1). The 8-wheel machine, with a constant total mass of 28 Mg (18 Mg machine weight + 10 Mg loading), trafficked section
192 1 and 2 of both operating trails, and made four passes.

193 Before the first machine pass, the initial surface was captured along 10 perpendicular transects on each of the four sections.

194 These transects, which were 4 m wide, were placed and marked permanently with inserted wooden pegs. The same pegs were
195 used to position the beam, which served as the reference height to measure profiles along each transect. Into this beam, metric
196 scales were inserted with a spacing of 10 cm in between, to note the distance between the surface and the beam to the nearest
197 cm. These measured distances (D0, [cm]) describe the surface along the transect on already existing machine operating trails,
198 prior to the trial conducted in this study. The same procedure was repeated after the fourth consecutive machine passes, giving
199 D4 [cm].

200 Next, the differences between D0 and D4 were calculated at each of the 41 measurements (10 cm spacing over 4 m) along a
201 transect. The maximum value of these differences, measured at the left or right machine track, was used to determine rut depth
202 (RD) [cm]. We used average values of both tracks to prevent pseudo replicates, since intraclass correlation coefficient was
203 high (0.83), when left and right tracks were integrated separately. Moreover, mean and maximum values of rut depth were
204 highly correlated (adj. $R^2 = 0.96$).

205 Volumetric soil moisture content was captured outside the 1st, 4th, 7th and 10th transect of each section, with a distance of 1 m
206 to the left and right track, at a depth of 10-15 cm. This water content was determined using 100 cm³ cores taken with an
207 undisturbed core sampler, with three replicates at each measurement. SWC_{CORE} was calculated according to equation (1):

$$SWC_{CORE}[\%] = \frac{M2 - M1}{M1} * 100 \quad (1),$$

208 with M2 being the fresh mass of the soil taken with undisturbed cores and M1 being the mass after drying the samples in oven
209 with 105 °C, until mass constancy was reached.

210 Measurements of RD and SWC_{CORE} were georeferenced using the GNSS device and complemented with all the predictor
211 variables, as described above.

212 **2.3 Selection of the final model and comparisons between model predictions and SWC_{CORE} or RD**

213 The study employed a stepwise elimination to remove predictor variables, resulting in (n-1) models, where n represents the
214 total number of available predictor variables. For each model, Kendall's coefficient of correlation τ was calculated, which
215 was obtained as the mean value resulting from repeated cross-validation. We used Kendall's rank correlation for all tests,
216 since different sample sizes occurred. To select the final random forest model for each data partition, we examined the
217 maximum τ values obtained and multiplied them by 0.99. This was done to penalize the use of an unnecessarily high number
218 of predictor variables. We selected the model with the least number of predictor variables within this 1%-range as the final
219 model. The final models were then used to make prediction rasters of SWC_{PRED} , which were visually evaluated.

220 Values of SWC_{PRED} were compared to soil water content, captured through undisturbed cores along the transects, SWC_{CORE} .
221 Therefore, the predictor variables added to the RD dataset were used to predict SWC_{PRED} by means of the final random forest
222 models created in the soil moisture modelling (Figure 2). Since the goodness-of-fit between in-situ values of RD or SWC_{CORE}
223 and SWC_{PRED} was to some degree sensitive to the seed set during modelling, we repeated the predictions ten times and used
224 average values to receive robust estimates of SWC_{PRED} . In addition, to ascertain the quality of all models in predicting rut
225 depth, RD was compared to SWC_{PRED} for each model during the feature reduction. To test the correlations between paired
226 samples of SWC_{CORE} or RD and SWC_{PRED} , Kendall's rank correlation was used. We illustrated the corresponding p-values as
227 follows: `****` for $p < 0.001$, `***` for 0.001-0.01, `**` for 0.01-0.05, `(*)` for 0.05-0.10 and 'ns' for p-values being higher than
228 0.10. Values are given as mean \pm standard deviation.

229

Figure 2: To predict soil water content (SWC, [%]), we trained models using two separate datasets: in-situ measurements using an impedance measuring technique (IMT) and continuously measuring soil sensor networks (SSN). The models used predictor variables derived from topographic indices (depth-to-water, topographic wetness index, stream power index, basin), soil maps (at 1:5,000 and 1:50,000 scales), SWC estimates from the ERA5-Land campaign (SWC_{ERA}), and numerical values for date (month and season). We performed cross-validation and reduced features stepwise to choose the best-performing model, which was then used to predict SWC for the positions and dates of different trials with a forwarder. SWC_{CORE}, measured in advance of the trials using undisturbed cores, and rut depth (RD, [cm]) were compared to model estimates from the final models of both datasets (IMT and SSN).

230 **3 Results**

231 **3.1 Soil water content**

232 Soil water content (SWC) was measured using a handheld moisture meter (IMT) during a field campaign launched in August
 233 2020. The mean value of SWC varied between 13.0±10% in August 2020 and 43.2±5.95% in February 2020 (Figure 3). Daily
 234 mean values obtained from SSN were similar to those obtained from IMT, ranging from 13.8±2.90% in September 2020 to
 235 39.1±6.66% in March 2020, in the period that corresponds to the one covered by IMT. The driest conditions were observed
 236 in September 2022, with a daily mean SWC of 12.7±2.55%. Overall, the results suggest that IMT and SSN provide comparable
 237 estimates of SWC, with the latter providing higher temporal resolution at a low spatial granularity.

238

Figure 3: The figure displays time series of soil water content (SWC) measured using a soil sensor network (A) with 18 measuring positions and manual measurements (B) conducted on 252 positions (black lines/points show daily mean values, grey shading/lines show standard deviation for each day). SWC retrievals from ERA5-Land are shown as a blue line/point ('layer 1', as available from Copernicus Climate Change Service (2019)) and a green line/point ('layer 2'). The goodness-of-fit between daily means of measured SWC and ERA5-Land retrievals is reported using Kendall's rank correlation coefficient (τ). Vertical lines indicate the dates of the trials when a forwarder conducted four passes at existing machine operating trials.

239 **3.2 Soil moisture models**

240 The positions IDs were used to select the 10 folds for cross-validation. However, the dataset SSN had only 18 measuring
 241 positions (where SWC was measured on 1116 days), resulting in relatively high deviations of the resulting R^2 of the random
 242 forests. The most important feature for this dataset was given by DTW025, although the resulting quality was low, with
 243 Kendall's coefficient of correlation τ of 0.363 ± 0.198 . By adding the temporal component Month, the Kendall's τ improved
 244 to 0.637 ± 0.065 , which had the lowest standard deviation for the repeated folds. The final model for this dataset included
 245 topographic predictor variables TWI, DTW2, Accumulation, DTW025 and SPI, as well as temporal variables including
 246 Month, SWC_{ERA2} , Year and Season (Figure 4). The resulting τ was 0.732 ± 0.128 , revealed through the cross-validation.

247 For the IMT partition, which had a low temporal but high spatial resolution, the most important feature was the temporal
 248 information SWC_{ERA2} , leading to a τ of 0.581 ± 0.045 . The final model had an τ of 0.622 ± 0.018 , including the predictor
 249 variables SWC_{ERA2} , Month, Season, and DTW025, Slope, SPI, TWI and DTW4.

250 Despite the low-quality model for the SSN partition, in which DTW025 was used as only predictor variable, the τ values for
 251 both partitions ranged from 0.581 ± 0.045 to 0.738 ± 0.128 , indicating a moderate level of predictability. Moreover, there was a
 252 slight positive effect with an increase in the number of predictor variables (or "depth" of trees in the random forest).

253

Figure 4: Soil water content (SWC) was modelled by random forests (RF), and evaluated by a repeated 10-fold cross validation (CV). Mean values and standard deviation of resulting values of the Kendall rank correlation coefficient τ during the CV are shown. A stepwise elimination of the least important variable was performed, and the frequency of this variable over all models is provided (“Feature reduction”). The vertical lines indicate the maximum value of τ (black) and the 99% of the maximum (grey), to select final models (squares). Variables used are described in section 2.

254 **3.2.1 Comparisons of SWC_{CORE} with SWC_{PRED}**

255 The final random forest models of both, the IMT and SSN dataset, were used to calculate SWC_{PRED} on the predictor variables
 256 of the rut depth data, including the soil water content SWC_{CORE} measured at the outside of a subsample of the measuring
 257 tracks by undisturbed cores. The comparison between SWC_{CORE} and SWC_{PRED} values predicted by the final random forest
 258 models of both datasets (SSN and IMT), revealed a significant association (Figure 5).

259

260

Figure 5: Soil water content was measured during two trials with a forwarder along a machine operating trail (n=14), using 100 cm³ undisturbed cores (SWC_{CORE}), and compared to values predicted (SWC_{PRED}) by a model trained data from a continuously measuring soil sensor network (SSN, A), or manual measurements with a handheld moisture meter (IMT, B). Correlations were evaluated using Kendall's τ and significance levels are indicated by *** for p<0.001, ** for 0.001-0.01, * for 0.01-0.05, (*) for 0.05-0.10, and 'ns' for p>0.10.

261 **3.3 Rut depth data**

262 Rut depth (RD, [cm]) was measured during four trials with a forwarder, covering 10 transects for each trial. This provided us
 263 with the potential for 40 measurements, but unfortunately, 4 of them were not ascertainable as the forwarder destroyed the
 264 wooden pegs that positioned the reference beam. In Trial 1, conducted in March 2011, SWC_{ERA1} and SWC_{ERA2} showed a
 265 soil moisture level of 39%. At Site 1, the measured RD was 10.3±1.9 cm, while at Site 2, the RD was 12.7±5.5 cm, with the
 266 highest value of RD recorded after 4 passes, with a depth of 21.5 cm. In Trial 2, conducted in October 2022, the soil water
 267 content from ERA5-Land was 32%. At Site 1, the measured RD was 3.5±1.7 cm, and at Site 2, the RD was 4.3±1.2 cm.

268 **3.3.1 Comparisons of RD with SWC_{CORE} and SWC_{PRED}**

269 RD was positively correlated with SWC_{CORE} when both trials with different moisture conditions were included in testing
 270 (Figure 6A). However, when each trial was tested separately, no correlation between RD and SWC_{CORE} was observed.
 271 Compared to the correlation between RD and SWC_{CORE}, modelling outputs SWC_{PRED} proved to be a better predictor of rut
 272 depth. The final models that were selected for both datasets produced a Kendall's τ coefficient of 0.63 (for IMT, Figure 6B,
 273 Figure 7) and 0.64 (for SSN, Figure 6C), when comparing RD of the four trials with the corresponding SWC_{PRED}. Although
 274 the R² values for these models were similar (0.60 for IMT and 0.65 for SSN), we chose to use Kendall's τ since different
 275 sample sizes were involved in the analysis. This was particularly relevant for comparing RD with SWC_{PRED} for each Trial
 276 separately. While no correlation could be found for Trial2, performed during dryer conditions, correlations were found for rut
 277 depth data of Trial1, with Kendall's τ of 0.35 (p=0.031) and 0.32 (p=0.051), for the final models trained on IMT and SSN,
 278 respectively (Figure 6B,C).

279

Figure 6: Rut depth (RD) was determined after four passes of a forwarder, driving on two Sites (1 and 2), during two seasons (Trial1 and Trial2). RD was compared to SWC values, determined for undisturbed soil cores (A) and SWC values predicted by a random forest model trained on manually obtained IMT measurements (B, see Figure 1) and predicted by a model trained data from a continuously measuring soil sensor network (SSN, C). Correlations were evaluated using Kendall's τ and significance levels are indicated by *** for $p < 0.001$, ** for 0.001-0.01, * for 0.01-0.05, (*) for 0.05-0.10, and 'ns' for $p > 0.10$.

280

Since the final model trained on IMT data performed slightly better in Trial1 compared to the model trained on SSN data (Figure 6), we chose the IMT model. Using this final random forest model, we generated prediction maps for the days when field trials took place. Figure 7 displays these rasters and reveals significant differences in SWC_{PRED} between Trial1 conducted on March, 2021 and Trial2 conducted on October, 2022.

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Figure 7: A random forest model was trained to predict soil water content based on spatial and temporal predictor variables. This model was then utilized to make raster predictions for the days when forwarder trials were conducted. The resulting rut depth after four passes is represented by coloured points, while the values of the rasters are displayed using a green-to-red gradient.

285 4 Discussion

286 4.1 Importance of predictive systems

287 Accurately predicting soil water content (SWC) and soil trafficability is essential for sustainable forest management and cost-
288 effective, environmentally friendly harvesting operations (Murphy et al., 2007; Vega-Nieva et al., 2009; White et al., 2012;
289 Mohtashami et al., 2017; Mattila and Tokola, 2019; Picchio et al., 2020; Uusitalo et al., 2020). Topographic modelling requires
290 minimal input and the temporal variables used in the final model presented here, are freely available (Copernicus Climate
291 Change Service, 2019). A spatiotemporal model predicting SWC could improve the guidance of machine operators in forest
292 sites during harvesting operations, for example by the effective positioning of brush mats (Labelle and Jaeger, 2018; Labelle
293 et al., 2019). Practical use of static, topographic maps has already been observed in Canada and Scandinavian countries (Ring
294 et al., 2022). By incorporating a temporal aspect, the accuracy of these tools could be further improved. This has the potential
295 to enhance sustainable forest management by protecting soil and mitigating harmful sediment transport (White et al., 2012;
296 Ågren et al., 2015; Kuglerová et al., 2017; Lidberg et al., 2020).

297 4.2 Comparison to previous work on predictions of SWC

298 Since soil moisture predictions are crucial for a variety of forestry aspects, several publications have focused on this topic
299 before. In a Swedish case study, Lidberg et al. (2020) predicted soil moisture classes using spatial models built on topographic
300 indices, correctly classifying 73% of wet areas. Ågren et al. (2014) reported accurate predictions for 87-92% of observations
301 by comparing soil moisture classes to DTW maps. Larson et al. (2022) used data from the Krycklan catchment and found an
302 accuracy of 84% when comparing moisture classes to the recently developed 'SLU soil moisture map' (Ågren et al., 2021).
303 However, these validations were based on static topographic maps. One attempt to make such static maps dynamic was
304 realized within the DTW concept, which can be customized to calculate various scenarios to adjust to general moisture
305 conditions (e.g., flow initiation areas of 0.25, 1, and 4 ha for wet, moist, and dry conditions, respectively), but selecting the
306 most appropriate scenario during practical use can be a challenging task that requires significant expertise (White et al., 2012;
307 Leach et al., 2017; Lidberg et al., 2020). To overcome this challenge, we aimed for improvement of soil moisture prediction
308 and refined the spatiotemporal approach conceived by Schönauer et al. (2022). During cross-validation of IMT data from sites
309 in Finland, Poland, and parts of the data used in this work, they reported an R^2 of 0.80. The models for the present study
310 showed an R^2 of 0.786 ± 0.191 (SSN) or 0.640 ± 0.045 (IMT), corresponding to Kendall's τ of 0.732 ± 0.128 or 0.622 ± 0.018 ,
311 respectively. Although this may not seem like an improvement, it should be noted that the data from German sites had less
312 explanatory power of topography for predicting SWC. For example, DTW4 alone explained SWC to a very limited extent (R^2
313 = 0.037^{***}).

314 4.3 Comparison to previous work on predicting rutting

315 Besides the comparisons of SWC with DTW maps, various studies have also investigated the capability of topographic indices
316 in predicting rutting – with conflicting outcomes. For example, Vega-Nieva et al. (2009) found that 65% of ruts deeper than
317 25 cm were located in areas with a vertical proximity to ground water of less than 1 m, while 93% occurred in areas with
318 DTW values less than 10 m. Similarly, Heppelmann et al. (2022) observed a high frequency of severe rut depth in areas with
319 DTW values less than 1 m in Norway. However, Mohtashami et al. (2017) did not find evidence of such patterns in a field
320 trial where the inclusion of DTW values did not improve the accuracy of a linear model to describe the extents and degrees

321 of rut depth on machine operating trails. In agreement, Schönauer et al. (2021a) found no evidence that DTW or TWI could
322 predict rut depth in a field trial conducted in a temperate broadleaved stand. In this study, we observed that the temporal
323 adjustments of the model based on current moisture conditions could improve predictions of rutting by up-to-date SWC
324 predictions. We observed a strong association between rut depth (RD) and predicted values of SWC, with an overall Kendall's
325 correlation coefficient (τ) at 0.63 (Figure 6). While no correlation was found between RD and SWC_{PRED} in Trial2, conducted
326 during relatively dry conditions (Figure 3, Figure 6A), a significant correlation was observed during Trial1, on relatively wet
327 conditions. Moreover, the ranges of RD for each trial were consistent with the SWC predictions (Figure 7), leading to an
328 overall improvement in the goodness-of-fit.

329 4.4 Description of the model

330 The best-performing model in predicting RD incorporated spatial information from DTW025, Slope, SPI, TWI and DTW4,
331 as well as temporal information from SWC_{ERAL2}, Month, Season, and was based on data from the manual measurements
332 (IMT). Soil information was excluded in the initial stages of feature reduction, likely due to the relatively homogenous soil
333 properties on the relatively small study sites. Surprisingly, the correlation between in-situ SWC_{CORE}, sampled directly at the
334 machine operating trails, showed a lower explanatory power in predicting RD than SWC_{PRED}. Although an overall association
335 between RD and SWC_{CORE} was confirmed, no correlation could be found when trials were analysed individually. This
336 indicates that the temporal variability in soil moisture between the trials was more important in this study than the spatial
337 variability within the relatively small areas where each trial was conducted.

338 The spatiotemporal model (IMT), also supports this conclusion as the temporal feature SWC_{ERAL2} was selected as most
339 important variable and the difference between the model with one predictor variable vs. the final model was small (Figure 4).
340 Still, this slight increase in the models' quality allowed for the integration of spatial patterns and resulted in the significant
341 prediction of RD in Trial1 ($\tau = 0.35^*$, Figure 6).

342 In this study there were negligible differences in performance between the models trained on the IMT dataset and those trained
343 on the SSN dataset, with Kendall's τ of 0.63 or 0.64, respectively. However, during Trial1, when the conditions were wetter,
344 the correlation between predicted SWC values using the IMT model and RD was slightly stronger. It's worth noting that the
345 IMT dataset only required a GPS device and a handheld moisture meter, while the SSN dataset relied on expensive sensor
346 networks positioned near the transects where the rutting was observed (Figure 1). Despite this, we argue that manual
347 measurements remain an appealing choice for collecting field data and could be facilitated by various forestry stakeholders.

348 4.5 Further developments

349 The terrain data was derived from a digital elevation model, which is increasingly available for the entire Europe (Hoffmann
350 et al., 2022), while the dynamic variables are based on date and retrievals from ERA5-Land, which are freely available up to
351 three days ago. These inputs would allow for automated mapping of soil water content, which could be made accessible to
352 forestry stakeholders, resulting in improved soil protection, higher efficiency of timber harvesting (Suvinen and Saarilahti,
353 2006), and a new stage of sustainable forest management (Campbell et al., 2013; Jones and Arp, 2019; Uusitalo et al., 2019;
354 D'Acqui et al., 2020). However, it should be noted that the in-situ data of SWC originated from manual measurements, and it
355 was relatively labor-intensive to gather this amount of data. There is potential to reach appropriate accuracy even with a
356 reduced dataset - further investigation would be necessary to determine the essential input data criteria. The alternative to

357 manual measurements is given by sensor networks, which led to comparable results (Figure 6), but such sensor networks are
358 expensive to establish and maintain. Nonetheless, initiatives of installing sensors are emerging and additional manual
359 measurements could be conducted. In the future, forestry stakeholders who require accurate raster predictions could
360 potentially facilitate manual measurements or install sensors (with focus on wet areas) and provide the captured data to
361 scientific organizations, which could deliver spatiotemporal soil moisture predictions in return. The captured data could be
362 made available for creating spatiotemporal models of SWC, allowing for additional training data and daily raster predictions
363 for new areas of interest, with various scientific insights and practical applications.

364 **5 Conclusion**

365 In this study, we developed a spatiotemporal model that used multiple topographic indices, temporal variables, soil moisture
366 retrievals from ERA5-Land, and data from manual measurements to predict soil water content (SWC). Predicted values of
367 SWC were compared to rut depth data collected during four forwarder trials. Overall, the model performed well in predicting
368 rut depth, with a Kendall's τ of 0.63 for all trials. This predictive capability could help forest managers and machine operators
369 avoid wet areas, leading to more sustainable forest operations. Using freely available temporal information is a significant
370 improvement, as it enables more accurate and up-to-date predictions, which allow to make more informed decisions and avoid
371 potential hazards. Future work should focus on developing automated pathways for generating daily raster predictions of
372 SWC, enabling day-to-day prediction rasters to be supplied and used. However, it should be noted that the models used are
373 always limited by the available data to be trained on. Therefore, there is a need for more data by manual measurements or the
374 establishment of additional sensor networks to cover more areas and different sites and regions. Additionally, the model's
375 predictive accuracy could be improved by obtaining more data on rut depth, which could be captured automatically by
376 machines driving off-road.

377 **Data availability**

378 The data used in this work will be made accessible via Zenodo

379 **Author contribution**

380 MS and DJ designed the experiments and MS and FH carried them out. MS developed the model code and performed the
381 simulations. MS prepared the manuscript with contributions from all co-authors.

382 **Competing interests**

383 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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399 6 Appendix

400 Appendix A

401 To model the dataset consisting of both IMT and SSN data, the procedure described in sections 2.1 and 2.3 was followed. The
402 IMT dataset was merged with a subsample of the SSN dataset, where the sample size of the SSN part was twice that of the
403 IMT dataset. This was done to prevent over-weighting of the SSN dataset. The resulting combination of IMT and SSN data
404 was called the "Mix" dataset.

405 The final model using the Mix dataset included the input variables SWC_{ERA2} , Month, TWI, Year, SWC_{ERA1} , Season,
406 DTW025, DTW2, Slope, SPI, and Accumulation, and achieved a τ of 0.659 ± 0.084 (which corresponded to R^2 values of
407 0.651 ± 0.117). Appendix A shows that the correlation between the model outputs (SWC_{PRED}) and rut depth (RD) was
408 significant.

409 Since the models trained on the Mix dataset did not perform better than those trained on the IMT or SSN datasets, we did not
410 investigate the fused data partition any further, as one research question addressed the use of different data origins. For future
411 work, however, the fused data would provide additional information, as compared to the individual datasets.

412

Supplementary Figure 1: Rut depth (RD) was determined after four passes of a forwarder, driving on two Sites (1 and 2), during two seasons (Trial1 and Trial2). RD was compared to SWC values predicted by a random forest model trained on data from manual measurements or captured through a continuously measuring soil sensor network ('Mix'). Correlations were evaluated using Kendall's τ and significance levels are indicated by *** for $p < 0.001$, ** for 0.001-0.01, * for 0.01-0.05, (*) for 0.05-0.10, and 'ns' for $p > 0.10$.

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414 **7 References**

- 415 Ågren, A., Larson, J., Paul, S. S., Laudon, H., and Lidberg, W. (2021). Use of multiple LIDAR-derived digital terrain indices
416 and machine learning for high-resolution national-scale soil moisture mapping of the Swedish forest landscape. *Geoderma*
417 404, 115280. doi: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115280
- 418 Ågren, A., Lidberg, W., and Ring, E. (2015). Mapping Temporal Dynamics in a Forest Stream Network—Implications for
419 Riparian Forest Management. *Forests* 6, 2982–3001. doi: 10.3390/f6092982
- 420 Ågren, A., Lidberg, W., Strömngren, M., Ogilvie, J., and Arp, P. (2014). Evaluating digital terrain indices for soil wetness
421 mapping – a Swedish case study. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 18, 3623–3634. doi: 10.5194/hess-18-3623-2014
- 422 Ala-Ilomäki, J., Lindeman, H., Mola-Yudego, B., Prinz, R., Väättäinen, K., Talbot, B., et al. (2021). The effect of bogie track
423 and forwarder design on rut formation in a peatland. *International Journal of Forest Engineering* 45, 1–8. doi:
424 10.1080/14942119.2021.1935167
- 425 Allman, M., Jankovský, M., Messingerová, V., and Allmanová, Z. (2017). Soil moisture content as a predictor of soil
426 disturbance caused by wheeled forest harvesting machines on soils of the Western Carpathians. *Journal of Forestry*
427 *Research* 28, 283–289. doi: 10.1007/s11676-016-0326-y
- 428 Ampoorter, E., van Nevel, L., Vos, B. de, Hermy, M., and Verheyen, K. (2010). Assessing the effects of initial soil
429 characteristics, machine mass and traffic intensity on forest soil compaction. *Forest Ecology and Management* 260, 1664–
430 1676. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2010.08.002
- 431 Awaida, A., and Westervelt, J. (2020). Geographic Resources Analysis Support System (GRASS GIS). USA: Geographic
432 Resources Analysis Support System (GRASS GIS) Software, <https://grass.osgeo.org>
- 433 Beylich, A., Oberholzer, H.-R., Schrader, S., Höper, H., and Wilke, B.-M. (2010). Evaluation of soil compaction effects on
434 soil biota and soil biological processes in soils. *Soil and Tillage Research* 109, 133–143. doi: 10.1016/j.still.2010.05.010
- 435 Bezirksregierung Köln (2020). *Digitales Geländemodell DGMI [Digital elevation model]*. Accessed November 08, 2021,
436 [https://www.bezreg-koeln.nrw.de/brk_internet/
437 geobasis/hoehenmodelle/digitale_gelaendemodelle/gelaendemodell/index.html](https://www.bezreg-koeln.nrw.de/brk_internet/geobasis/hoehenmodelle/digitale_gelaendemodelle/gelaendemodell/index.html)
- 438 Bivand, R. S. (2021). rgrass7: Interface Between GRASS 7 Geographical Information System and R, [https://CRAN.R-
439 project.org/package=rgrass7](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rgrass7)
- 440 Breiman, L. (2001). Random forests. *Machine Learning* 45, 5–32. doi: 10.1023/A:1010933404324
- 441 Cambi, M., Certini, G., Neri, F., and Marchi, E. (2015). The impact of heavy traffic on forest soils: A review. *Forest Ecology*
442 *and Management* 338, 124–138. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2014.11.022
- 443 Campbell, D. M.H., White, B., and Arp, P. (2013). Modeling and mapping soil resistance to penetration and rutting using
444 LiDAR-derived digital elevation data. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation* 68, 460–473. doi: 10.2489/jswc.68.6.460
- 445 Carranza, C., Nolet, C., Pezij, M., and van der Ploeg, M. (2021). Root zone soil moisture estimation with Random Forest.
446 *Journal of Hydrology* 593, 125840. doi: 10.1016/j.jhydrol.2020.125840
- 447 Cavalli, A., Francini, S., McRoberts, R. E., Falanga, V., Congedo, L., Fioravante, P. de, et al. (2023). Estimating Afforestation
448 Area Using Landsat Time Series and Photointerpreted Datasets. *Remote Sensing* 15, 923. doi: 10.3390/rs15040923
- 449 Chen, T., He, T., Benesty, M., Khotilovich, V., Tang, Y., Cho, H., et al. (2021). *xgboost: Extreme Gradient Boosting*.
450 Accessed November 09, 2021, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=xgboost>
- 451 Copernicus Climate Change Service (2019). *ERA5-Land hourly data from 2001 to present*. ECMWF.

452 Crawford, L. J., Heinse, R., Kimsey, M. J., and Page-Dumroese, D. S. (2021). Soil Sustainability and Harvest Operations.
453 *General Technical Report RMRS*. doi: 10.2737/RMRS-GTR-421

454 Curzon, M. T., Slesak, R. A., Palik, B. J., and Schwager, J. K. (2022). Harvest impacts to stand development and soil properties
455 across soil textures: 25-year response of the aspen Lake States LTSP installations. *Forest Ecology and Management* 504,
456 119809. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119809

457 D'Acqui, L. P., Certini, G., Cambi, M., and Marchi, E. (2020). Machinery's impact on forest soil porosity. *Journal of*
458 *Terramechanics* 91, 65–71. doi: 10.1016/j.jterra.2020.05.002

459 DeArmond, D., Ferraz, J., and Higuchi, N. (2021). Natural Recovery of Skid Trails. A Review. *Canadian Journal of Forest*
460 *Research*. doi: 10.1139/cjfr-2020-0419

461 Eijkelkamp Agrisearch Equipment (2013). *User Manual for the Moisture Meter type HH2*. Accessed August 07, 2020,
462 https://www.eijkelkamp.com/download.php?file=M1142602e_Soil_moisture_meter_flab.pdf

463 Eliasson, L. (2005). Effects of forwarder tyre pressure on rut formation and soil compaction. *Silva Fennica* 39, 549–557. doi:
464 10.14214/sf.366

465 Francesca, V., Osvaldo, F., Stefano, P., and Paola, R. P. (2010). Soil Moisture Measurements: Comparison of Instrumentation
466 Performances. *J. Irrig. Drain Eng.* 136, 81–89. doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9437(2010)136:2(81)

467 Gröll, M. (2011). Den Waldboden schonen–Vorsorgender Bodenschutz beim Einsatz von Holzerntetechnik [Soil protection
468 in forest operations]. *Eberswalder Forstliche Schriftenreihe* 47, 37–44.

469 Guo, M., Li, J., Sheng, C., Xu, J., and Wu, L. (2017). A Review of Wetland Remote Sensing. *Sensors (Basel)* 17. doi:
470 10.3390/s17040777

471 Hansson, L., Šimůnek, J., Ring, E., Bishop, K., and Gärdenäs, A. I. (2019). Soil Compaction Effects on Root-Zone Hydrology
472 and Vegetation in Boreal Forest Clearcuts. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. j.* 83, 239. doi: 10.2136/sssaj2018.08.0302

473 Heppelmann, J. B., Talbot, B., Antón Fernández, C., and Astrup, R. (2022). Depth-to-water maps as predictors of rut severity
474 in fully mechanized harvesting operations. *International Journal of Forest Engineering* 33, 108–118. doi:
475 10.1080/14942119.2022.2044724

476 Heubaum, F. (2015). *Bodenschutz im Staatsbetrieb Sachsenforst [Soil protection]: Projekte zur Technologieerprobung*.
477 Accessed November 05, 2021, https://www.sbs.sachsen.de/download/Bodenschutz_Projekte_2015_09_30.pdf

478 Hijmans, R. J. (2020). raster: Geographic Data Analysis and Modeling, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=raster>

479 Hillel, D. (1998). *Environmental soil physics: Fundamentals, applications, and environmental considerations*. San Diego,
480 California: Elsevier.

481 Hoffmann, S., Schönauer, M., Heppelmann, J., Asikainen, A., Cacot, E., Eberhard, B., et al. (2022). Trafficability Prediction
482 Using Depth-to-Water Maps: the Status of Application in Northern and Central European Forestry. *Curr Forestry Rep* 338,
483 124. doi: 10.1007/s40725-021-00153-8

484 Horn, R., Vossbrink, J., Peth, S., and Becker, S. (2007). Impact of modern forest vehicles on soil physical properties. *Forest*
485 *Ecology and Management* 248, 56–63. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2007.02.037

486 Jones, M.-F., and Arp, P. (2017). Relating Cone Penetration and Rutting Resistance to Variations in Forest Soil Properties
487 and Daily Moisture Fluctuations. *Open Journal of Soil Science* 07, 149–171. doi: 10.4236/ojss.2017.77012

488 Jones, M.-F., and Arp, P. (2019). Soil Trafficability Forecasting. *Open Journal of Forestry* 9, 296–322. doi:
489 10.4236/ojf.2019.94017

490 Kemppinen, J., Niittynen, P., Riihimäki, H., and Luoto, M. (2018). Modelling soil moisture in a high-latitude landscape using
 491 LiDAR and soil data. *Earth Surf. Process. Landforms* 43, 1019–1031. doi: 10.1002/esp.4301

492 Koen Hufkens, Reto Stauffer, and Elio Campitelli (2019). *khufkens/ecmwfr: ecmwfr*. Zenodo.

493 Kristensen, J. A., Balstrøm, T., Jones, R. J. A., Jones, A., Montanarella, L., Panagos, P., et al. (2019). Development of a
 494 harmonised soil profile analytical database for Europe: a resource for supporting regional soil management. *SOIL* 5, 289–
 495 301. doi: 10.5194/soil-5-289-2019

496 Kuglerová, L., Hasselquist, E. M., Richardson, J. S., Sponseller, R. A., Kreutzweiser, D. P., and Laudon, H. (2017).
 497 Management perspectives on Aqua incognita : Connectivity and cumulative effects of small natural and artificial streams
 498 in boreal forests. *Hydrological Processes* 31, 4238–4244. doi: 10.1002/hyp.11281

499 Kuhn, M. (2020). *caret: Classification and Regression Training*. Accessed November 09, 2021, [https://CRAN.R-](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=caret)
 500 [project.org/package=caret](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=caret)

501 Kursa, M. B., and Rudnicki, W. R. (2010). Feature Selection with the Boruta Package. *J. Stat. Soft.* 36. doi:
 502 10.18637/jss.v036.i11

503 Labelle, E. R., and Jaeger, D. (2018). Management Implications of Using Brush Mats for Soil Protection on Machine
 504 Operating Trails during Mechanized Cut-to-Length Forest Operations. *Forests* 10, 19. doi: 10.3390/f10010019

505 Labelle, E. R., Poltorak, B. J., and Jaeger, D. (2019). The role of brush mats in mitigating machine-induced soil disturbances:
 506 An assessment using absolute and relative soil bulk density and penetration resistance. *Canadian Journal of Forest*
 507 *Research* 49, 164–178. doi: 10.1139/cjfr-2018-0324

508 Larson, J., Lidberg, W., Ågren, A. M., and Laudon, H. (2022). *Predicting soil moisture conditions across a heterogeneous*
 509 *boreal catchment using terrain indices*.

510 Leach, J. A., Lidberg, W., Kuglerová, L., Peralta-Tapia, A., Ågren, A., and Laudon, H. (2017). Evaluating topography-based
 511 predictions of shallow lateral groundwater discharge zones for a boreal lake-stream system. *Water Resources Research* 53,
 512 5420–5437. doi: 10.1002/2016WR019804

513 Lidberg, W., Nilsson, M., and Ågren, A. (2020). Using machine learning to generate high-resolution wet area maps for
 514 planning forest management: A study in a boreal forest landscape. *Ambio* 49, 475–486. doi: 10.1007/s13280-019-01196-9

515 Mattila, U., and Tokola, T. (2019). Terrain mobility estimation using TWI and airborne gamma-ray data. *Journal of*
 516 *environmental management* 232, 531–536. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.11.081

517 McNabb, D. H., Startsev, A. D., and Nguyen, H. (2001). Soil Wetness and Traffic Level Effects on Bulk Density and Air-
 518 Filled Porosity of Compacted Boreal Forest Soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 65, 1238–1247. doi:
 519 10.2136/sssaj2001.6541238x

520 Mohtashami, S., Eliasson, L., Jansson, G., and Sonesson, J. (2017). Influence of soil type, cartographic depth-to-water, road
 521 reinforcement and traffic intensity on rut formation in logging operations: a survey study in Sweden. *Silva Fennica* 51. doi:
 522 10.14214/sf.2018

523 Moore, I. D., Grayson, R. B., and Ladson, A. R. (1991). Digital terrain modelling: A review of hydrological,
 524 geomorphological, and biological applications. *Hydrol. Process.* 5, 3–30. doi: 10.1002/hyp.3360050103

525 Murphy, P. N. C., Ogilvie, J., and Arp, P. (2009). Topographic modelling of soil moisture conditions: A comparison and
 526 verification of two models. *European Journal of Soil Science* 60, 94–109. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2389.2008.01094.x

527 Murphy, P. N. C., Ogilvie, J., Connor, K., and Arp, P. (2007). Mapping wetlands: A comparison of two different approaches

528 for New Brunswick, Canada. *WETLANDS* 27, 846–854. doi: 10.1672/0277-5212(2007)27[846:MWACOT]2.0.CO;2

529 Murphy, P. N. C., Ogilvie, J., Meng, F.-R., White, B., Bhatti, J. S., and Arp, P. (2011). Modelling and mapping topographic
530 variations in forest soils at high resolution: A case study. *Ecological Modelling* 222, 2314–2332. doi:
531 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2011.01.003

532 Oliveira, V. A., Rodrigues, A. F., Morais, M. A. V., Terra, M. d. C. N. S., Guo, L., and Mello, C. R. (2021). Spatiotemporal
533 modelling of soil moisture in an Atlantic forest through machine learning algorithms. *Eur J Soil Sci* 72, 1969–1987. doi:
534 10.1111/ejss.13123

535 Picchio, R., Latterini, F., Mederski, P. S., Tocci, D., Venanzi, R., Stefanoni, W., et al. (2020). Applications of GIS-Based
536 Software to Improve the Sustainability of a Forwarding Operation in Central Italy. *Sustainability* 12, 5716. doi:
537 10.3390/su12145716

538 Poltorak, B. J., Labelle, E. R., and Jaeger, D. (2018). Soil displacement during ground-based mechanized forest operations
539 using mixed-wood brush mats. *Soil and Tillage Research* 179, 96–104. doi: 10.1016/j.still.2018.02.005

540 Quinn, P., Beven, K., Chevallier, P., and Planchon, O. (1991). The prediction of hillslope flow paths for distributed
541 hydrological modelling using digital terrain models. *Hydrol. Process.* 5, 59–79. doi: 10.1002/hyp.3360050106

542 Ring, E., Ågren, A., Bergkvist, I., Finér, L., Johansson, F., and Högbom, L. (2022). *A guide to using wet area maps in forestry:
543 En guide för hur man kan använda markfuktighetskartor i skogsbruket*. ARBETSRAPPORT 1051-2020. Uppsala, Sweden.

544 Schönauer, M., Hoffmann, S., Maack, J., Jansen, M., and Jaeger, D. (2021a). Comparison of Selected Terramechanical Test
545 Procedures and Cartographic Indices to Predict Rutting Caused by Machine Traffic during a Cut-to-Length Thinning
546 Operation. *Forests* 12, 113. doi: 10.3390/f12020113

547 Schönauer, M., and Maack, J. (2021). R-code for calculating depth-to-water (DTW) maps using GRASS GIS (Version v1).
548 *Zenodo*. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5638518

549 Schönauer, M., Prinz, R., Väätäinen, K., Astrup, R., Pszenny, D., Lindeman, H., et al. (2022). Spatio-temporal prediction of
550 soil moisture using soil maps, topographic indices and SMAP retrievals. *International Journal of Applied Earth
551 Observation and Geoinformation* 108, 102730. doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2022.102730

552 Schönauer, M., Väätäinen, K., Prinz, R., Lindeman, H., Pszenny, D., Jansen, M., et al. (2021b). Spatio-temporal prediction
553 of soil moisture and soil strength by depth-to-water maps. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and
554 Geoinformation* 105, 102614. doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2021.102614

555 Sirén, M., Salmivaara, A., Ala-Ilomäki, J., Launiainen, S., Lindeman, H., Uusitalo, J., et al. (2019). Predicting forwarder rut
556 formation on fine-grained mineral soils. *Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research* 34, 145–154. doi:
557 10.1080/02827581.2018.1562567

558 Sørensen, R., and Seibert, J. (2007). Effects of DEM resolution on the calculation of topographical indices: TWI and its
559 components. *Journal of Hydrology* 347, 79–89. doi: 10.1016/j.jhydrol.2007.09.001

560 Suvinen, A., and Saarilhti, M. (2006). Measuring the mobility parameters of forwarders using GPS and CAN bus techniques.
561 *Journal of Terramechanics* 43, 237–252. doi: 10.1016/j.jterra.2005.12.005

562 Uusitalo, J., Ala-Ilomäki, J., Lindeman, H., Toivio, J., and Sirén, M. (2019). Modelling soil moisture – soil strength
563 relationship of fine-grained upland forest soils. *Silva Fennica* 53. doi: 10.14214/sf.10050

564 Uusitalo, J., Ala-Ilomäki, J., Lindeman, H., Toivio, J., and Sirén, M. (2020). Predicting rut depth induced by an 8-wheeled
565 forwarder in fine-grained boreal forest soils. *Annals of forest science* 77. doi: 10.1007/s13595-020-00948-y

- 566 Vega-Nieva, D. J., Murphy, P. N. C., Castonguay, M., Ogilvie, J., and Arp, P. (2009). A modular terrain model for daily
567 variations in machine-specific forest soil trafficability. *Canadian Journal of Soil Science* 89, 93–109. doi:
568 10.4141/CJSS06033
- 569 Walker, J. P., Willgoose, G. R., and Kalma, J. D. (2004). In situ measurement of soil moisture: a comparison of techniques.
570 *Journal of Hydrology* 293, 85–99. doi: 10.1016/j.jhydrol.2004.01.008
- 571 White, B., Ogilvie, J., Campbell, D. M.H., Hiltz, D., Gauthier, B., Chisholm, H. K., et al. (2012). Using the Cartographic
572 Depth-to-Water Index to Locate Small Streams and Associated Wet Areas across Landscapes. *Canadian Water Resources*
573 *Journal* 37, 333–347. doi: 10.4296/cwrj2011-909
- 574 Wright, M. N., and Ziegler, A. (2017). ranger: A Fast Implementation of Random Forests for High Dimensional Data in C++
575 and R. *J. Stat. Soft.* 77. doi: 10.18637/jss.v077.i01
- 576